

The Role of the Church in the Economic Development of Nigeria

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Abstract

The church as a social institution plays an important role in the spiritual and socio-economic development of its members and the society at large. The issue of economic development is of national concern. The Nigerian economy had a truncated history from independence to present times and the economy has suffered series of economic instability because of a long period of unsustainable growth in the per capital real income of the country accompanied by lack of fundamental changes in the structure of the economy. This article intends to highlight the role of the church in economic development. This study adopted the secondary data drawn from an array of published and unpublished materials relevant to the study. Major findings of this study shows that the church's impact on governments is one of the most important ways it has helped Nigeria as a nation. The result of the study further revealed that the church has historically served as a trusted advisor to government officials offering moral compass and a foundation for ethical leadership rooted in religious values. The study concludes that churches are playing a significant role in developing the societies in which they are established hence, contributing towards economic development. The study recommends the need for churches to identify areas of importance in the economy such as the manufacturing industry so that they can channel resources towards establishing enterprise that could improve the nation's Gross Domestic Product. Furthermore, there is the need for the government to fully support the church for an enhanced sustainable national development.

Keywords: Church, Economy, Economic Development

Introduction

The church has a critical role to play in the economic development of any country. The Christian churches in Nigeria have in the past driven a crusade to provide education to people. In most countries the education system that exists has its roots in the church. The primary goal of the church right from the time of its inception has been the propagation of the Gospel; she has also been concerned with the wellbeing of her members. However, her concern in recent times has gone beyond the narrow confines of the wellbeing of her members to embrace the larger society¹. In order to meet up with her concern for larger society, she has created agencies and arms involved in various aspects of development needs spanning various sectors, such as education, health, housing, care for the poor, conscience formation as well as other social and political needs. The paper therefore, intends to highlight the role of the church in the economic development of Nigeria.

The Church

The word Church is derived from the New Testament. Therefore, the Christian church is a New Testament Institution that begins with the Pentecost and ends with the Rapture.

There are two words of special importance:

- i. "Ecclesia" – is from the Greek words meaning "to call out from". The word 'Ecclesia' is used three (3) times in the New Testament, denoting a secular sense in Acts 19:39² "it shall be determined in a lawful assembly of Israel in the wilderness" (Acts 7:38)³ and of the assembly of believers in Jesus Christ (Mathew 16:18, 18:17, 1 Corinthians 1:2)⁴. In keeping with this idea, the Saints are said to be the "call out ones" (Rom 8:30, 1 Corinthians 1:2)⁵

- ii. “Kuriakon” means that which belongs to the Lord that is ‘the Supper of the Lord’ (1 Corinthians 11:20)⁶, ‘The day of the Lord’ (Rev. 1:10)⁷. Therefore, the idea of the growth of the church in the New Testament suggests that at first, there was but one church at Jerusalem, headed by the Apostles. The church later on spread throughout Judea and Samaria (Acts 8:1)⁸. The church at Antioch in Syria became the headquarters of the Gentile church (Acts 13:1). As a result of the missionary activities of the Apostles, churches sprang up in different cities, especially in Asia Minor which comprises Corinth, Galatia, Ephesus and Philippi.

In view of these, the term church came to be used as the church universal meaning ‘the complete body of Christ’ (1 Corinthians 15:9, Gal 1:12-13, Matt 16:18)⁹

The Nigerian Church

The Nigerian church includes the following: the Mainline Churches, African Independent Churches, The Roman Catholic Church and the Pentecostal Churches. So, the church in Nigeria refers to the entire Christian faithful, whether they are laymen or women religious group, Clergy and their organizational structure or entities. This church is a portion of the Universal Church in peculiarities with the reference to ecclesiastical communion and that of the New Religious Movements. These New Religious Movements are those groups and bodies established sometime in the 20th and 21st Centuries as alternatives to the official institutional churches. Others comprise those that represent a ‘return to paganism’ and others still of agnostic status.¹⁰

The Concept of Economy

An economy is usually religion-based, for instance, a country or a town, and it comes down to the resources or wealth held by the said region. We can also define economy as how a nation produces goods and services and consumes them. Therefore, the word ‘economy’ refers to how well the consumption and production occur as well as the quality of the goods and services. An economy shows how a religion makes and spends its money. It includes not just the production of goods and services but also the organizations and institutions that play a vital role in the production. Companies/organizations could help in the processing or manufacture of products and other companies or individuals that consume them¹¹. In other words, an economy is an area of the production, distribution and trade as well as consumption of goods and services. That is, an economy is a social domain that emphasizes the practices and material expressions associated with the production, use and management of scarce resources.

The Concept of Economic Development

Economic development is programs, policies or activities that seek to improve the economic wellbeing and quality of life for a community. What economic development means to you will depend on the community you live in. Each community has its own opportunities, challenges and priorities. In development economics, the term economic development is commonly used. Economic development is the process by which there is a long period of sustained growth, accompanied by fundamental changes in the structure of the economy and an overall sustained improvement in the material wellbeing of the people. Economic development occurs if the rate of growth of real per capital income in the country is higher than the rate of growth of population over a long time period of time. That means an expansion of health and educational services and more persons having access to them. Economic development is followed by an increase in life expectancy and standard of living.¹² “Economic development is the process of growth in total and per capital income accompanied by fundamental changes in the economy.”¹³

Economic development is relevant to underdeveloped countries, because these third world countries are concerned with how to develop and use their unknown and unused resources, it therefore requires some sort of planning and guidance to keep the forces of expansion in a particular direction, for instance, by increasing life expectancy which means by consciously planning and directing resources in the area of health

services.¹⁴ Qualitative change is the heartbeat of economic development. It is only when there is an increase in the quality of life. Food output and real income and so on, that we can say that economic development have taken place. Economic development in essence produces economic growth.

Theoretical Framework

This paper used the theory of social responsibility as a model in the analysis of research evidence in order to explain the contribution of the Church in the economic development of Nigeria. The theory of social responsibility is an ethical theory in which individuals are accountable for fulfilling their civic duty, and the actions of individuals must benefit the entire society¹⁵. In this way, there must be a balance between economic growth and the welfare of the society and the environment. Therefore, if this equilibrium is maintained then social responsibility is accomplished. The theory of social responsibility is built on a system of ethics, in which decisions and actions must be ethically validated before proceeding. If the action or decision causes harm to the society and the government, then, it would be considered to be socially irresponsible¹⁶. In the submission of Guthrie,¹⁷ social responsibility aspect of religion is what creates the foundation of laws and social structure for a society to evolve overtime. Social responsibility is not out of Church's purview. It is the heart of the gospel of Jesus Christ, which is all about 'giving to others' as recorded in John 3:16.¹⁸

Nigeria Economic Outlook

Recent Macroeconomic and Financial Developments

In Nigeria, real GDP growth fell to 3.3% in the year 2022 from 3.6% in 2021, precipitated mainly by a decline in oil production. This led to 5% shrinkage in overall industry, which was offset by expansion in services 7% and agriculture 2%. On the demand side, the decline in GDP growth was driven by contraction in public consumption (2.5%) and not exports (80%) Growth in income per capital decline to 0.8% from 1.2% in 2021. The fiscal deficit narrowed to 4.9% to GDP in 2022 from 5.2% in 2021 and was financed by borrowing, bringing public debts to \$103.1 billion (about 22% of GDP) from \$92.6 billion in 2021. Inflation peaked at a two decade high of 18.8% fueled by energy and food price increases and pass through effects of exchange rate depreciation. The central bank of Nigeria successively raised the policy rate, which peaked at 16.5% in November 2022 from 11.5% at the start of the year to time rising inflation. Buoyed by relative improvement in oil exports, the current account recorded a small surplus of 0.1% of GDP in 2022 reversing three years of deficit. Gross International Reserves decline 7.5% to \$37.1 billion (5.7% months of Import cover). The non-performing loans ratio stood at 4.2% in 2022. The multi-dimensional poverty rate (63%) and unemployment 33.3% remained high¹⁹.

The Christian Church and Economic Development in Nigeria

Throughout its long history, the church has been a major source of social services like schooling and medical care; an inspiration for art, culture and philosophy and an influential player in politics and religion. In various ways it has sought to affect western attitudes towards values and virtues in diverse fields. The role that the church ought to play in socio-economics transformation or development is the empowering role, where the church organizes workshops, seminar and conferences on socio-economic challenges and how to address them.

The church also provide the necessary resource for sustaining and expanding various aspects of church life, including worship services, outreach programs pastoral care and community engagement. By embracing tithing and offerings, churches also ensure financial stability and facilitate economic growth to support their mission. The contribution of the church to the overall development of Nigeria has been inculcating uncompromised moral values, respect for human life and dignity through adequate education, provision of medical services, development of national language and agricultural development.

Adequate Education

The Christian missionaries embarked on conversation through education. This helped them to penetrate the people who they converted, trained and empowered to become trainers of others²⁰. Collaborated the fact saying that “western education had been identified as probably the most important motive for the acceptance of Christian missions. At the initial stages of missionary work in Nigeria, the European missionaries offered rudimentary education. Adult converts were thought church doctrines and catechism. The missionaries also taught the people how to rear different types of animals.

Medical Services

Admittedly, medical ministration started early in the wake of the missionary enterprise in Nigeria. It began as a result of many sicknesses that were prevalent in those days fever, dysentery, leprosy, sores and wounds. The patients were nursed within the church premises; subsequently the Christian missionaries built hospitals in different places within the country²¹. He further asserted that: demonstration against the current needy condition of the human society, hence the church came out and began to impact the society through a display of love and patriotism.

Development of National Languages

The use of African literature and languages was of primary importance in founding missions in Africa. The missionaries realized early to establish an efficient Christian mission in Africa, the gospel should be preached in the language of the converts. Therefore, they began on time to develop the African languages, which they used to transmit Christianity and civilization. Onyeidu remarked that interest in the study, teaching and translation of west African languages which had enriched the world culture of the people began in Sierra Leon; starting from 1804 when the church missionary society (CMS) occupied Sierra Leone; it instructed its agents to learn the native language in order to learn facilitate evangelism in the area.²² “The study of Igbo language, according to Tasié “was began by John F. Schon, the German Philologist and Missionary who for his linguistic achievements was in 1844 to receive the DD of Oxford, he had reduced Igbo to writing in 1841.”²³ “Crowther concentrated on the Yoruba language and not only wrote a grammar of the language but also translated part of the Bible for their worship, thus, it was possible for the Yoruba mission to have a vernacular Bible as early as 1884.”²⁴

Agricultural Development

The significant role of the church in the development of agriculture can never be ignored. Thus; speaking on the role of agriculture to the economic development of Nigeria, Onuora asserts that:

Agriculture has gone along way to produce food for man and animals in Nigeria. And the church has given its supports for the benefit of its members and the country at large. Consequently, it is the source materials for the domestic industrious and for exports. Above all, agriculture has paved way for entrepreneurs to become involve. Owing to this fact, it is important for the church to always teach “all hands on the plough” for economic development.²⁵

Indeed the Christian church has been and is still contributing to every strata of the country’s economic development.

Impediments to the Role of the Church towards Economic Development in Nigeria

In Nigeria, the economy has not been stable; the government has not met its target as regards the provision of social amenities. Rather, it has been from one problem to another ranging from political instability, insecurity, uneven distribution of wealth and unaffordable cost of medication. Despite the efforts of the church towards economic development of the nation, there are some challenges. These are poor educational systems,

poor political climate, poverty and unemployment. Poor Educational System: This is practically seen in much emphasis given to theory than practical lessons; for instance, most Nigerian engineers have more theoretical knowledge of handling construction work and mechanics, this is because the system of education trains them to be job seekers and not job makers that would help them to create more employment for the people so as to make them acquire the basic necessities of lives.

Another hindrance to economic growth in Nigeria is poor political climate. This factor has kept the country in problem such as low production, high inflation rates, corruption, kidnapping, farmers and herders clash, insurgency and armed banditry. Other problems include: poverty, unemployment, poor technology/production methods used, high illiteracy rates, high population growth rates, thus, increasing the dependency rates within families, damping by the developed economics which kills the initiative to develop and expand local industries, high rates of profit repatriation by foreign investors within the developing economics, dependency on the developed world, high level of deficit management which worsen their salaries of payment position and poor terms of trade in the world market.²⁶

Conclusion

The contribution of the church to the economic development of Nigeria cannot be ignored. The dividends are seen in the areas of education, politics, health and economics etc. There is no limit to the various ways in which the church has contributed to the economic development of Nigeria. This is significant especially at this time in the world when the church in Africa appears to be at the centre of evangelization. Although a great deal has been achieved, there are still robust and dominant roles open for her in the economic, social, political and other segments of development of the Nigerian society.

Recommendations

1. There is the need for the Christian churches in Nigeria to identify the areas of importance in the economy such as the manufacturing industry so that they can channel resources towards establishing enterprises that could improve the nation's Gross Domestic Product.
2. Entrepreneurship education should be encouraged by the government and should be made a compulsory course in Nigerian higher institutions.
3. There is the need for the Christian churches in Nigeria to constantly renew herself and her objectives as an institution.
4. Since, the church and the government are concerned with the total development of man and his society. It is expedient that both of them should partner to achieve success, whereas, the church organizations are augmenting government efforts in providing social amenities, government should do well to financially support them to execute their projects. Such partnership will not only increase the speedy rate of socio-economic development but will also enhance the quality of the developmental projects that each group may want to execute.
5. A synchronic approach to Church and development should be conducted. Such a study would mainstream theories, concepts and designs that would guide researchers who are more interested in the Church as universal and not local or particularized churches.
6. More mainstreaming of existing studies is required in order to inform and enrich theory and practice of the universal Church in socio-economic development.

Endnotes

¹Okechukwu Onwuliri, *The Theory and Practice of Capital Market* (Wolsak Publishers, 2008).

²*New Living Translation Study Bible* (Tyndale House Foundation, 1996).

³Ibid.

⁴Ibid.

⁵Ibid.

⁶Ibid.

⁷Ibid.

⁸Ibid.

⁹Ibid.

¹⁰Benedict Etafo, "Ecclesiastical Communion and the New Religious Movements in Nigeria: Some Selected Colonial Issues," *Bodija Journal* 6 (1994): 3-4.

¹¹"Economy/Definition," accessed September 21, 2023, <https://www.Economy/Definit...Study.Com>.

¹²Abiodun Falodun and Kenneth Nnadi, *New Approach in Economics* (Emancon Publishers, 2007),

¹³Clara Oguji and Tage Kene, *Foundation of Development Studies* (West and Solomon Publishers, 2009).

¹⁴Joseph Inwelegbu, *A Test in Economics* (Kajon Publishers, 2011),

¹⁵Daniel Eck, *A New Religious America: The World's Most Religiously Diverse Nation* (London: Harper One Press, 2002),

¹⁶Barnea Amir and Rubin Amir, "Corporate Social Responsibility as a Conflict between Shareholders," *Journal of Business Ethics* 19 (2013),

¹⁷Donald Guthrie, "New Testament Approach to Social Responsibility," *Vox Evangelica* 8 (2003),

¹⁸*New Living Translation Study Bible* (Tyndale House Foundation, 1996),

¹⁹"AfDB Nigeria Economy," accessed September 21, 2023, <https://www.afdb.Nigeria.econ>.

²⁰Ebiegberi Joe Alagoa, "The Eastern Niger Delta and the Hinterland in the 19th Century," in *Ground Work of Nigerian History*, ed. Ikeme (Heinemann, 1999),

²¹Hillary Achiike, *The Dreams of Heaven: A Modern Response to Christianity in North West North Igbo Land 1970–1990* (African-FEP Publishers Limited, 2002),

²²Sunday Onyiedu, *Christianity and Onitsha Primal Religion: The Anglican Contribution* (Magnet Business Enterprise, 2001),

²³G. Tasie, "John Christopher Taylor: A Biographical Note," in *The Major Mission: Origin, Growth and Impact 1857–1995*, ed. Adiele (1996), 70.

²⁴Emmanuel Ayodele, *The Missionary Factor in Northern Nigeria 1879–1918*, accessed July 12, 1966, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4185610?seq=20>.

²⁵Onyechi Onuora, "Hands on the Plough," (paper presented at the CHC International Youth Conference, Gymnasium Hall, 2012).

²⁶Infocare.com, accessed September 21, 2023, <https://www.Infocare.com/search>.